

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO INCREASE THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

The article provides in detail that the indicator of the quality of Education directly depends on the quality of teachers' activities. What should be taught to students is established by state standards, programs. Well, "how to teach?" the answer to the question "" should be sought only in the professional training of the teacher, in the ability to plan his own business, in the ability to predict and see his real goals and organize the child's actions."

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The indicator of the quality of education is directly related to the quality of teachers' work. What should be taught to students is determined by state standards and programs. And, "how to teach?" the answer to the question should be sought only from the professional training of the teacher, the ability to plan his work, the skill of predicting and seeing his specific goals and organizing the child's actions.

The main person in the development of school work and student achievements is the teacher. Requirements for the teacher's professional level (professional knowledge, skills and abilities) are provided in the description of professional qualifications.

Professional qualifications are the stages of professional training of an employee, allowing them to perform a certain level of work duties in a particular type of activity. That is, qualification is a set of requirements for the level of theoretical and practical experience.

Professional development is a teacher's participation in professional development activities and education through special educational programs in order to effectively perform his/her duties and to raise his/her professional level.

The Institute carries out professional development activities in two directions: in courses and inter-course events. These works are reflected in theoretical lectures, interactive seminars and practical classes.

Pedagogical activities and situations are created in the system of professional development of the teacher for self-determination, strengthening of competition,

formation of competence. It is aimed to form the subject-theoretical, methodological, methodological preparation and research culture and professional competence of each student through practical trainings and seminars.

One of the main concepts in modern pedagogic science is the concept of "competence". American scientist N. Chomsky, who first defined the term "competence" and introduced it into science. "Competence" (Latin word) competence means capable, concerned. Competence is the presence of knowledge, skills, business, willpower in a person, student and includes such concepts as "knowledge", "ability" and "skill". That is, competence is the ability to use acquired knowledge and skills in practice, in everyday life to solve some practical and theoretical problems, the result of education reflected in the quality of the student's actions. Subject competence is a qualitative set of knowledge, skills, abilities and actions related to certain subjects in educational activities, the ability to use the foundations of pedagogical and social psychology.

In the theoretical lectures, the listeners get acquainted with the conditions for a new evaluation of the educational achievements of students, and they share their ideas about the criteria for the new evaluation of the educational achievements of the students and share their experiences. This increases the effectiveness of the courses. And in the practical lessons they learn to plan lessons, to differentiate tasks, to work with extended, competence tasks. At the end of the course, listeners will defend their projects and others will evaluate

them. It contributes to the productivity and effectiveness of the courses.

Tasks of competence type are composed as follows: stimulus-situation; formulated task; source of information; filling sheet (answer sheet); inspection tool; response sample. The stimulus situation motivates the student to complete the task. The conditions of the problem, which are the basis for describing the situation or sources of information, are considered. The source of information should be relevant, interesting and appropriate for the learning age. Checking how well the tester performed the assigned tasks in which areas. Sample answer - correct and possible answers, key - samples of student answers, answer form - the process of the student's activity to complete the task.

On the basis of this information, the trainees will compile competence tasks through group work and work on small projects. The group of experts and other groups will evaluate the created competence tasks.

The use of competence tasks in the classroom helps the teacher to solve several tasks at the same time during the lesson: to determine the level of development of key competences of students; determining the level of development of subject knowledge and skills; assessment of the child's ability to independently acquire knowledge and choose methods of action in order to achieve the goal set in the task; formation of interest in the subject through the development of research.

Pupils learn how to read, and as a result, they become free, able to convincingly present their own arguments, motivated, reliable, have systematically developed critical views, and are formed as individuals who are proficient in digital technologies.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, from 2012 to 2016, level courses were conducted in the direction of improving the qualifications of teaching staff, and from 2016 to 2021, courses were conducted on the programs of updating the content of secondary education. That is, in the period from 2012 to 2021, courses on improving the subject competence of teachers were not held in the country. In order to improve the quality of education and fill this gap, the "Orleu" National Center for Pedagogical Development" has recently been developing training programs in a new format within the scope of subject competencies and focusing on conducting advanced training courses. In addition, large-scale work is being carried out in the direction of increasing the quantitative competence of teaching staff.

In August-October 2021, all teachers of the country passed distance learning courses on the topic "Development of Digital Competence of Teachers" prepared by "Orleu" National Center for Pedagogical Development". Teachers of Kyzylorda region participated in this course and were certified.

Between March 2021 and March 2022, a distance learning course was organized for English language teachers under the Future English Online Teacher Community Program within the framework of cooperation between the JSC "Orleu" NCPD" and the British Council International Organization in order to improve the subject competence of teachers. Within the framework of the project, 2,000 English language teachers of general education schools in the country passed the

course. The training was free of charge and English language teachers were required to have at least B1 level of English to participate in the training. 125 English language teachers participated in Kyzylorda region, and according to the test results, 26 of them successfully completed the course and received international certificates.

Between May 3 and June 15, 2022, the best trainers of Orleu, together with the EdCrunchAcademy company, studied the principles of creating programs and educational-methodological complex for the development of educational programs within the framework of subject competencies, and created their own author's programs.

The authors of the program mastered the methodology of developing educational programs and the basics of testology using the principle of reverse design, and formulated the goals, objectives and expected results during the development of educational programs. Based on the learning results, the design work of practical and assessment tasks.

44 educational programs were developed in 12 subjects such as mathematics, computer science, physics, chemistry, biology, geography, natural science, Kazakh, Russian and English languages, history and primary classes.

From August 1, training courses for subject teachers began in "Orleu" branches in all regions of the country. 46,340 teachers are scheduled to undergo courses to increase their subject competence by November 18 under 44 programs developed in accordance with modern requirements for all classes. Among them, 2925 trainees in Kyzylorda region will improve their qualifications.

Before starting the courses, the teachers undergo a diagnostic test on the digital platform. Diagnostic testing helps to determine the level of subject knowledge of teachers before the start of courses and to evaluate the effectiveness of educational programs. Based on the results of training in the courses, the analysis of the effectiveness of teaching and the final assessment of their acquired knowledge are carried out in order to improve the qualifications of teachers. International experience shows that educational programs aimed at increasing subject competences have a positive effect on the professional development of teachers and the increase in the quality of their work. It also contributes to the increase of the general quality of education, including the student's educational index.

In the courses, it is aimed to form the subject-theoretical, methodological, methodical preparation and research culture and professional competence of each student through practical trainings and seminars. In the theoretical lectures, the listeners get acquainted with the conditions for a new evaluation of the educational achievements of students, and in the seminars, they share their ideas about the criteria for the new evaluation of the educational achievements of the students and share their experiences. This increases the effectiveness of the courses. And in the practical lessons organized by the methods and forms of active learning, they learn to plan competence lessons, to differentiate in the lesson, to work with extended, competence tasks. At the

end of the course, students will defend their projects in these areas, and others will evaluate them. That is, the effectiveness and efficiency of the courses increases, subject teachers receive professional education and improve their professional qualifications. This is an effective way to improve quality.

References:

1. Ivanov D.A., Mitrofanov K.G., Sokolova O.V. Competence approach in education. Problems, concepts, tools: Educational and methodological manual. Science, Academia APKPRO 2005. - 182 p.
2. Turganbekova B.A. "Development of teacher's creative potential in the context of professional development: theory and practice." - Almaty: Rauan, 2005. - 250 p.
3. Vorovshchikov S.G. "Educational and cognitive competence of schoolchildren". Management of the modern school. - №6, 2007. - 81 p.